

Agricultural Practices and Sustainable Development of Char Area, with Special Reference to Darrang District, Assam

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The development of agricultural activities in India reflects the spectrum of socio-economic variation of different socio-cultural groups. It is the art and science of cultivating the soil, growing crops and raising livestock. "Assam economy is primarily an agrarian economy with 80 percent of its population engaged in agriculture and allied activities. The main source of livelihood of the rural areas is agriculture, especially rain fed paddy cultivation. Traditional agriculture had always been a way of life and subsistent-oriented. But with the passage of time and advancement of farming system, there is a strong need to shift out the traditional production-oriented approach to market oriented approach to meet the demand and increase the farmers income level. The Char areas of Darrang district are highly rich in the agricultural sector. Mainly winter crops are practiced in the Char areas of Darrang district. Sustainable development of the area is solely dependent on conservation, management and judicious use of natural resources of the area. The tremendous population pressure in the Char areas on arable land may be considered as one of the most important aspects of sustainable development issue. The paper is also devoted to study about the sustainable development in the Char areas. The intrinsic meaning of sustainable development implies the ethical imperative of equity within and between generation, which goes beyond the mere satisfaction of basic human needs.

Keywords: Agriculture, Char, Sustainable, development, ethical.